
Government Initiatives by the Ministry of MSME to Empower Small Businesses in India

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Abstract:

This paper examines the initiatives and policies put in place by India's Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) to support in the expansion and advancement of small enterprises. MSMEs contribute significantly to economic growth and job creation. The study focuses on how these enterprises benefit from the Ministry's policies, which facilitate their access to markets, technology, and funding. It also covers the important role of Micro, small and Medium Enterprises in Indian economy. The study examines several government programs and how they affect MSMEs, emphasizing their advantages, disadvantages, and potential areas for development. Overall, the study highlights how crucial it is for the government to keep supporting MSMEs so they can expand and make a greater economic contribution to India.

Keywords- MSME, Employment, Economy, Export.

Introduction:

Usually, small-scale industries are those that use tiny machinery and a small workforce to manufacture, produce, and provide services. These businesses have to abide by the rules established by the Indian government. Particularly in emerging nations like India, the SSI is the backbone of the economy. These sectors contribute significantly to job generation since they are often labor-intensive. Because they contribute to per capita income and resource use in the economy, SSI are an important sector of the economy from both a financial and social standpoint. Small businesses are often owned by a single person or occasionally by a partnership. The proprietor actively participates in the daily operations of the company. Our industrial structure is based on small-scale industries. The creation of jobs, an improvement in living standards, and an increase in income are the main goals of small business development. Bakeries, school supplies, water bottles, leather belts,

little toys, paper bags, picture studios, and beauty salons are a few examples of small-scale businesses.

In India, the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) is the government agency in charge of creating and carrying out policies, plans, and projects meant to encourage the expansion of MSMEs in the nation. The Ministry seeks to establish an environment that encourages innovation, entrepreneurship, and the creation of jobs in the MSME sector.

Through the state government's directorate of industries, the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) offer SSI registration. To be eligible for certain benefits, a business must register for SSI. Programs, grants, and other rewards offered by the government. Establishing a new SSI firm in India is the primary justification for SSI registration.

The Government of India oversees the Ministry of MSME, which collaborates with many departments and groups to put

policies and programs that assist MSMEs throughout the country into action. The Ministry works with a number of ministries and performs a number of tasks to foster an atmosphere that is favorable to the expansion of MSME.

Objectives:

1. To study the role of Micro, small and Medium Enterprises in Indian economy.
2. To analyze the policies of Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSME).

Research Methodology:

To accomplish research objectives to conduct this study, required data have been collected from secondary sources. Secondary data collected from reference books, journals, internet, research papers and relative thesis.

Review of Literature:

1. Priyadarshan Zanjurne (2018) Published research paper titled, "Growth and future prospects of MSME in India." This study examines government initiatives to regenerate the MSME sector and to evaluate the overall growth and development in the MSME sector in India. Researchers concluded that MSME contributed about 40% of total exports of the country, 45% industrial unit, 42 million employments and more than 8000 products in Indian economy.

2. Dr. Ch. Hema Venkatasivasree & Dr. P. Vasari (2020) made a study on, "MSME in India-growth and challenges." The goal of this research paper is to know the problems faced by MSME in India. According to the researcher MSME facing many challenges like the unawareness towards technological advancement, low cost credit to the MSME and foreign banks are not taking so much interest in sanctioning loan to the MSME sector.

3. Soni Rathi & Dr. Praveen Kumar (2022) published a research paper titled, "The impact of micro, small and medium enterprises on Indian economy in India." The objective of this research paper is to determine the contribution of micro, small and medium enterprises in country's economy (2014-2021)." Based on their findings it is stated that the segment of micro, small and medium enterprises has contributed negatively to business production, employment and trade of the nation.

4. Rubinabibi Farukh Shaikh & Dr. Farida Rusi Mandviwala (2023) Published research article titled, "A systematic literature review on role of micro, small and medium enterprises in Indian economy." The goal of this research paper is to assess the opportunities and challenges associated with micro, small and medium enterprises based on literature review. According to the researcher MSME face several challenges-difficulty to review timely finance for working capital, lack of sophisticated technology, non-availability of skilled workforce and poor infrastructure facility.

Role of Micro, small and Medium Enterprises in Indian economy:

In many respects, micro, small, and medium-sized businesses are crucial to the growth of the Indian economy. The MSME sector in India is responsible for between 60 and 70 percent of all inventions. Below is a quick explanation of MSME contribution to the nation's economic development-

1. Job Creation: The foundation of employment generation in India is MSMEs. Millions of people are employed by these companies, which include local service providers, manufacturers, and small stores. MSMEs employ a large number of people dispersed over many industries and regions, in contrast to large organizations that could only have a small number of workers in one place. In smaller towns and villages where

job opportunities are more limited, MSMEs offer jobs. People can find work closer to home, which reduces the migration from rural to urban areas.

2. Export Potential: MSMEs assist India in exporting, or selling goods to other nations. Many small enterprises manufacture specialized or distinctive products that are sought after in international markets. Products like clothing, handicrafts, food items, and electronics can fall under this category. These companies can generate foreign exchange by exporting to countries outside of India. MSMEs contribute to the nation's economy by exporting goods. This is significant because export revenue contributes to the growth of India's foreign exchange reserves, which are necessary to keep the country's economy stable.

3. Contribution to GDP: A significant amount of India's economy is composed of a variety of goods and services that are produced by MSMEs. Food, garments, electronics, handicrafts, and services like healthcare and education are all included in this. MSMEs immediately contribute to the GDP through the goods and services they produce. By assisting larger industries, MSMEs also indirectly contribute to the GDP. Many large corporations depend on small companies for parts, services, or supplies. This establishes a connection between small and large enterprises, and the GDP of the nation is increased by the total value of their output.

4. Encouraging Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurs with fresh concepts or inventive solutions for issues frequently lead MSMEs. Small firms are allowed to try out new goods, services, and business strategies, unlike large corporations that could have rigid policies and procedures. This adaptability fosters originality and innovation. MSMEs give people a place to launch their own companies. Whether they are in manufacturing, retail, services, or

technology, many entrepreneurs start out by establishing small enterprises. These tiny companies support economic growth and enable people to follow their entrepreneurial aspirations.

5. Supporting Local Communities: MSMEs frequently concentrate on generating employment in the neighborhood. They improve the well-being of the neighborhood and employ locals. This implies that persons in underserved or smaller areas can also take advantage of job possibilities that might not otherwise be accessible. MSMEs provide opportunities for success to persons from a variety of social backgrounds. Opportunities that may not be available in larger, more organized firms are frequently provided by MSMEs.

Policies of Ministry of MSME:

One of the most dynamic and vibrant sectors of the Indian economy is the Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector. The MSME Ministry operates a number of programs aimed at offering marketing support, infrastructural development, skill development training, and credit and financial aid. The following shows the Ministry of MSME's main policies-

1. Credit Guarantee Fund Scheme (CGS): A government program called the Credit Guarantee Fund Scheme (CGS) aims to assist small enterprises (MSMEs) in obtaining loans without having to provide collateral, such as real estate or other assets, as security. All MSMEs, whether they are manufacturing, service, or retail, are eligible for the program. The normal range of loans handled by CGS is between ₹10 lakh and ₹2 crore.

2. Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP): A government program called the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Programme (PMEGP) supports entrepreneurs in launching their own micro-

enterprises (small firms) with the goal of creating jobs. It offers financial support to individuals who wish to launch new businesses, particularly in urban and rural areas. The scheme is open to all individuals, but **special categories** like women, Scheduled Castes (SC), Scheduled Tribes (ST), and backward classes may get extra benefits or subsidies.

3. Stand-Up India Scheme: To promote entrepreneurship among women and members of scheduled castes (SC) and scheduled tribes (ST), the Indian government introduced the Stand-Up India Scheme in 2016. The program's objective is to give them the chance to launch their own businesses and achieve independence. In the industrial, service, or trading industries, the loans are intended to assist in the establishment of greenfield enterprises—new companies that have never been before. To launch their own company, entrepreneurs can borrow anything from ₹10 lakh to ₹1 crore.

4. Udyam Registration: Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Businesses (MSMEs) in India can register online with ease using Udyam Registration. It assists companies in becoming recognized as MSMEs, which entitles them to a range of government assistance, programs, and advantages. A number of government programs, including credit guarantees, subsidies, and easy loans, are available to registered enterprises.

5. Credit Link Capital Subsidy Scheme: The CLCSS is a government program that offers financial assistance to Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Businesses (MSMEs) so they can upgrade their technology. In order to help MSMEs modernize their operations and increase production, the program provides a discount on loans they take out to purchase new machinery, equipment, and technology. There are subsidies of up to 15% available for the acquisition of new machinery and plants. The subsidy is offered on loans up to one crore rupees.

6. MSME Cluster Development

Programme: The Government of India launched the MSME Cluster Development Programme with the goal of enhancing the general competitiveness, quality, and productivity of Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) in certain clusters, or industries. A cluster is a collection of MSMEs that operate in the same sector or are situated in the same region. These companies frequently share resources, expertise, and markets, making them interdependent. The cluster development program's objective is to assist these companies in expanding collectively, exchanging knowledge, enhancing their infrastructure, and gaining access to funding and technology.

Conclusion:

The growth, development, and sustainability of the MSME sector in India are significantly influenced by the policies of the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME). The Ministry has made a substantial contribution to MSMEs' empowerment by easing their access to capital, technology, and market opportunities through a number of programs and projects. In addition to increasing MSMEs' competitiveness, the measures have aided in inclusive economic growth, rural development, and job creation. MSMEs have benefited greatly from the Ministry's initiatives, but their continued significant economic contribution to India will depend on ongoing oversight, flexibility in response to shifting market conditions, and efficient implementation. Future changes should concentrate on lowering operational barriers, encouraging innovation, and making sure that policy objectives and the actual requirements of MSMEs at the grassroots level are more closely connected.

References:

1. Soni Rathi & Dr. Praveen Kumar (2022), “The impact of micro, small and medium enterprises on Indian economy in India”, Journal of Kavikulaguru Kalidas Sanskrit University Ramtek, Volume 09 Issue 02 (129-140).
2. Dr. Ch.Hema Venkatasivasree & Dr. P. Vasari (2020), “MSME in India-growth and challenges”, Journal of Scientific Computing, Volume 09 Issue 02 (126-137).
3. Priyadarshan Zanjurne (2018), “Growth and future prospects of MSME in India”, International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science, Volume 04 Issue 08 (608-614).
4. Rubinabibi Farukh Shaikh & Dr. Farida Rusi Mandviwala (2023), “A systematic literature review on role of micro, small and medium enterprises in Indian economy”, International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology, Volume 10 Issue 04 (407-413).